

WP5-Task T5.4

RESTORE Use-Cases Modelling Summary

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036766.

PROJECT INFORMATION SHEET	
Project Acronym	RESTORE
Project Full Title	Renewable Energy based seasonal Storage Technology in Order to Raise Environmental sustainability of DHC
Grant Agreement	101036766
Call Identifier	H2020-LC-GD-2020-1
Topic	Innovative land-based and offshore renewable energy technologies and their integration into the energy system
Project Duration	48 months (October 2021 – September 2025)
Project Website	www.restore-dhc.eu
Disclaimer	The sole responsibility for the content of this document lies with the authors. It does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the funding authorities. The funding authorities are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained herein.

DELIVERABLE INFORMATION SHEET	
Number	<p>(D5.4.0): The current report contains general information about “RESTORE Use-Cases Modelling”, related to WP5 Task T5.4, dealing with implementation, optimization, management & validation of the six RESTORE Use-Cases, using the Simulation Web Platform.</p> <p>This document is publicly available in the RESTORE’s Zenodo Community account https://zenodo.org/communities/101036766/records.</p>
Full Title	WP5-Task T5.4 - RESTORE Use-Cases Modelling Summary
Related WP	WP5 (RESTORE EU-wide Replication in Virtual Representation on Real Use-Cases)
Related Task	Task 5.4 (Implementation, optimization, management & validation of RESTORE Use-Cases using the Simulation Web Platform), and related Sub-tasks ST5.4.1; ST5.4.2; ST5.4.3; ST5.4.4; ST5.4.5; and ST5.4.6.
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Dissemination level	Public
Due Date	Due date for the 6 Deliverables: July 2025 (M46)
Submission Date	July 31 st , 2025
Status	Version 1.0

QUALITY CONTROL ASSESSMENT SHEET			
ISSUE	DATE	COMMENT	AUTHORS
V0.1	14/10/2023	Draft_Version 01	Fatima Dargam (SIMTECH)
V0.2	20/11/2023	Draft_Version 02 Review	Erhard Perz (SIMTECH)
V0.3	27/11/2023	Reviewed Version	Fatima Dargam (SIMTECH)
V0.4	10/07/2025	Version Updates	Stefan Bergmann (SIMTECH)
V1.0	31/07/2025	Final Reviewed Version	Fatima Dargam (SIMTECH)
V1.0	31/07/2025	Review + Submission in the EC Portal & Zenodo	Francisco (CENER) Thilo Walser (SOLITES)

Summary

This document summarizes the development of WP5 task T5.4 on “Implementation, optimization, management & validation of RESTORE Use-Cases using the Simulation Web Platform”, led by SIMTECH with close cooperation with the Use-Cases Providers.

This report supports Results of task T5.4 reported in month M46 of RESTORE project, via the Deliverables:

- D5.4: Implementation and validation of RESTORE Use-Case I: Residential / Industrial DH with Biomass and Solar Collectors.
- D5.5: Implementation and validation of RESTORE Use-Case II: Integration of different heat sources in DH of Cement Industry.
- D5.6: Implementation and validation of RESTORE Use-Case III: Integration of different heat sources in DH of Paper Mills Industry.
- D5.7: Implementation and validation of RESTORE Use-Case IV: Integration of different heat sources in DH of Steel-working industry.
- D5.8: Implementation and validation of RESTORE Use-Case V: District heating with Geothermal Technology.
- D5.9: Implementation and validation of RESTORE Use-Case VI: Small-scale DHC network of Politecnico di Milano campus.

The main purpose of this report (in version 1.0) is to describe the preliminary specifications for the six Use-Cases modelling, within the RESTORE virtual tool powered by the IPSE GO simulation web-platform.

The information provided in this document builds upon collaboration between SIMTECH and all RESTORE development partners, in the sense that it considers inputs not only from other tasks of WP5, but also from work packages WP1, WP2, WP3 and WP4.

As an open science publication from RESTORE project, this report is available in the project's Zenodo Community account (<https://zenodo.org/communities/101036766/records>).

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1. Introduction

This document summarizes the development status of WP5 task T5.4 on “Implementation, optimization, management & validation of RESTORE Use-Cases using the Simulation Web Platform”, led by SIMTECH with close cooperation with the Use-Cases Providers. Results of task T5.4 are to be reported in month M46 via the Deliverables D5.4, D5.5, D5.6, D5.7, D5.8 and D5.9, respectively related to the Use-Cases:

- Use-Case I: Residential / Industrial DH with Biomass and Solar Collectors.
- Use-Case II: Integration of different heat sources in DH of Cement Industry.
- Use-Case III: Integration of different heat sources in DH of Paper Mills Industry.
- Use-Case IV: Integration of different heat sources in DH of Steel-working industry.
- Use-Case V: District heating with Geothermal Technology.
- Use-Case VI: Small-scale DHC network of Politecnico di Milano campus.

The purpose of this report (in version 1.0) is to describe the preliminary specifications for the six Use-Cases modelling, within the WP5-T5.4, using the RESTORE virtual tool powered by the IPSE GO simulation web-platform. The information provided in this document builds upon collaboration between SIMTECH and all RESTORE development partners, in the sense that it considers inputs not only from other tasks of WP5, but also from work packages WP1, WP2, WP3 and WP4.

2. Task T5.4

WP5 task T5.4’s main objective is to implement each of the defined RESTORE Use-Cases using the Simulation Web Platform, for their further optimization, management, as well as validation within the RESTORE Virtual Tool, using the overall process model of the project technology implemented using the IPSEpro simulation environment. Task T5.4 is composed of 6 sub-tasks (ST5.4.1-ST5.4.6) covering the specific virtual representations of the 6 Use-Cases I, II, III, IV, V and VI.

Figure 1: WP5 Task T5.4 Structure.

As stated in [1], in task T5.4 the simulated RESTORE Use-Cases, defined by the providers; AAL, CEN, AND, TUR and POL, are configured and made available as interactive models in the IPSE GO Web-based Simulation Platform, which once customized for the project’s needs, caters for the virtual implementation, simulation and optimization of all Use-Cases. The experience from partner UBB will be used to implement also a quantification of the environmental impact. It will be made available to a wider audience of end-users and stakeholders related to the virtual Use-Case provided. Using the platform, end-users will be able to adapt Use-Cases according to their requirements via their web browsers, as well as to create and contribute with new Use-Cases, multiplying the impact of the project’s concept validation. Thus, within the work delivered in task T5.4, SIMTECH will ensure that the Use-Cases are available as interactive models in the RESTORE Virtual Tool, powered by IPSE GO web-based simulation platform. T5.4 will also deliver an estimate (with the support of the cooperation with UBB) a quantification of the environmental impact of the virtual Use-Cases.

WP5-T5.4

Figure 2; Task T5.4 Timeline.

Task T5.4 started in month M25 (October 2023) and is supposed to deliver its final results in M46. Pro-action for Task T5.4: Since the 1st RESTORE GA Meeting in Nov.2022 in Spain on month M14, SIMTECH has already requested the involved project partners to provide a general configuration information of the installations of the Use-Cases (in their current status), to contribute for structuring the work on task T5.4. The planned work phases followed within task T5.4 are listed below.

WP5 – Task T5.4 Work Phases:

- **Phase 1 - M25** – Organization of the work within T5.4. Production of task summary for the acquisition of relevant data for implementing the Use-Cases (SIMTECH)
- **Phase 2 - M26-M28** – Interactions with the Use-Case Providers and their representatives in RESTORE, to define the modelling of the Use-Cases with real data from their installations, using the specifications of Deliverable D1.4 [3], via group and individual collaboration meetings. (SIMTECH, AAL, TUW, CEN, AND, TUR and POL).
- **Phase 3 - M29-M31** – Creation of customized models for the implementation of the Use-Cases, using the IPSEpro-MDK Model development Kit. Preliminary modelling of the Use-Cases implemented together with the Use-Cases Providers within the RESTORE Virtual Tool, powered by IPSE GO. (SIMTECH, AAL, TUW, CEN, AND, TUR and POL).
- **Phase 4 - M32-M39** – Further development of the Use-Cases, implemented and shared with all Use-Cases Providers and project partners via the RESTORE Virtual Tool, powered by IPSE GO. (SIMTECH, AAL, TUW, CEN, AND, TUR and POL).
- **Phase 5 - M30-M46** – Continuous interactions with selected stakeholders, via organized events together with partners from WP6 and WP7, to perform the steps of the “Replication Strategy via Stakeholders Test-Cases” planned in WP5 task T5.5 (see D5.10 [8]), using the current results of the modelled Use-Cases.
- **Phase 6 - M35-M43** – Interaction with partner UBB to implement the quantification of the estimated environmental impact of the RESTORE Use-Cases. (UBB, SIMTECH, AAL, TUW, CEN, AND, TUR and POL).
- **Phase 7 - M40-M46** – Further development of the Use-Cases, implemented and shared with all Use-Cases Providers and project partners via the RESTORE Virtual Tool, powered by IPSE GO. (SIMTECH, AAL, TUW, CEN, AND, TUR and POL).
- **Phase 8 - M46** – Submission of the Deliverables D5.4, D5.5, D5.6, D5.7, D5.8 and D5.9, with the respective implementation results of RESTORE the Use-Cases I, II, III, IV, V and VI. (SIMTECH, AAL, TUW, CEN, AND, TUR and POL).
- **Phase 9 - M46-M48** – Main focus: (1) Collection of feedback from the Use-Case Providers (potential early adopters of the RESTORE technology) about the virtually implemented Use-Cases using the RESTORE Virtual Tool. (2) Interaction with partners from WP6 and WP7 for tasks related to the dissemination and exploitation of the project using the results of the modelled Use-Cases.

Within the periods stated above, several meetings were organized among partners involved in the Use-Cases. The meetings were mostly done individually per Use-Case. The collaboration meetings foreseen in Phase 6 happened involving all Use-Cases providers in the same group.

The results from task T5.4 are fundamental for the successful implementation of WP5 task T5.5, concerning the “Replication Strategy via Stakeholders Additional Test-Cases” [8].

3. The Simulation Tools in RESTORE

The overall goal of the simulation within RESTORE includes the precise behavioural and numerical representation of the involved components and process models, at a high accuracy level in relation to the real data provided / acquired, so that their evaluation and implementation within real-data virtual use-case scenarios can be validated.

The RESTORE concept will be validated both in lab-scale, and also via virtually represented applications with district heating and cooling networks. At a first stage, the consistency of the specific component models is checked and validated with the partners' experience largely obtained from the experimental activities within the project. Then, those component models are used for building the virtual demonstrations. Those virtual demonstrations represent showcases of real use-cases allowing the simulation of the project concept in scaled-up scenarios. For this to happen, the overall RESTORE system will be virtually implemented and optimized using SIMTECH's simulation tools (IPSEpro and IPSE GO), and incorporated in the six specific Use-Cases defined for the project. Refer to D1.4 [3] for a detailed description of the simulation tools (IPSEpro, IPSEpro-MDK, IPSEpro-PSE, and IPSE GO) used in RESTORE, as well as for the explanation of how the six Use-Cases representations will be made publicly available online.

For the sake of powering the RESTORE Virtual Tool, the cloud-based simulation platform IPSE GO (<https://about.ipsego.app/>) uses the capabilities of the process simulation system IPSEpro via the web, and was designed to run in all internet browsers, from any device you may wish to work with (computers, mobile devices, etc.). In addition, it is based on an intuitive user interface that can handle the complexity of the industrial level within a user-friendly way. A strong advantage of using IPSE GO is the "effortless collaboration" aspect that it offers to all its users.

3.1. The RESTORE-Virtual Tool

The RESTORE Virtual Tool, powered by IPSE GO, enables the showcase of RESTORE's overall process model solution, the performance evaluation of the Use-Cases interactively; making the results available to a wider audience of end-users, stakeholders related to the defined virtual Use-Cases segments. The RESTORE simulated process models will be made available online, via their internet browsers, without the need for any software installation.

The RESTORE Virtual Tool allows end-users to adjust the Use-Cases according to their requirements, using the platform via web browsers. Additionally, using IPSE GO, the platform users will be able to investigate new testing cases, multiplying the impact of the project's concept validation.

In *Annex I. RESTORE Virtual Tool powered by IPSE GO*, and in *Annex II. RESTORE Virtual Tool – Projects Page*, you find larger graphic detail of both Figure 3 and Figure 4.

Horizon 2020 RESTORE Project Model Library

General	87 Available Units	Example Projects
<p>RESTORE – Renewable Energy based seasonal Storage Technology in Order to Raise Economic and environmental sustainability of DHC</p> <p>RESTORE proposes a radically innovative solution for DHC, based on the combination of two key innovative technologies, that allows integrating a wide variety of renewable technologies combined with competitive seasonal storage in DHC networks, allowing them to be 100% renewable to radically improve their environmental sustainability.</p> <p>The first technology the project aims to develop is an innovative thermal energy storage system based on thermochemical reactions, the Thermochemical Energy Storage (TCES), that provides daily and seasonal competitive energy storage due to its high energy density, very low energy losses and its low cost. The system represents a key development due to the fact that it allows harnessing the enormous amount of energy that is normally wasted due to the mismatch between energy demand (loads) and energy generation (related to the availability of renewable resources or waste heat), mainly occurring between seasons. In addition, the project aims to develop a second technology based on Heat Pump (HP) and Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) combined with the TCES system. This second technology adapts the energy provided by different renewable technologies to feed the storage system, thus a wide variety of renewable technologies and waste heat can be integrated into the whole system to finally supply the energy demand under the specific conditions laid down by each DHC.</p> <p>This radically innovative solution would tackle the main barriers to a wide deployment of renewable energy technologies and waste heat in the existing and future DHC networks. The project considers the experimental validation of the RESTORE concept and also the demonstration of the concept replicability potential, adapting and optimizing the proposed solution to different real sites (different network conditions and local particularities as the available renewable technologies/waste heat) spread over the EU, and quantifying its potential benefits via virtual use-cases.</p> <p>Additional information about the project can be found here: https://www.restore-dhc.eu/</p>		
		<p>Author SimTech GmbH</p> <p>Keywords Thermochemical Energy Storage, TCES, Organic Rankine Cycle, Reversible Organic Rankine Cycle, Heat Pump, District Heating, District Cooling, Horizon 2020</p> <p>Version 1.0.22</p> <p>Resources Library Manual</p>

Figure 3: RESTORE Virtual Tool powered by IPSE GO.

IPSE GO

NAVIGATION

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- Projects**
- Groups
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SETTINGS

- Profile
- Preferences

My Projects **Example Projects**

Search...

<p>RESTORE rORC with TCES</p> <p>Demonstration model of the reversible ORC process for charging and discharging interaction with</p>			
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Figure 4: RESTORE Virtual Tool showing some RESTORE process models.

The implementation of the RESTORE process models using the simulation tool IPSE GO follow the specifications and requirements of relevant aspects like feasible computational

effort, object-oriented philosophy, compatibility between models, and adaptability to the web-platform, modularity and flexibility, which align with the definitions in WP1-T1.4. Hence, the RESTORE Virtual Tool presents the following characteristics: Usability; System Robustness; as well as Sharing, Portability, Compatibility, and Security related to collaborating Project-Files.

3.1.1. RESTORE Preliminary Simulated Models

The current process models available in the RESTORE Virtual Tool include the Thermo-chemical Storage (TCES) Charging Model, and the TCES Discharging Model. In Annex III and in Annex IV you find illustrations of both RESTORE TCES charging and discharging process models. See D1.4 [3] for more details.

The process models are designed with component models from the project library RESTORE_Lib. RESTORE component models were implemented and fine-tuned within WP5-T5.1 and WP5-T5.3 with input from WP1, WP2 and WP3. Extensions and updates of both RESTORE_Lib and process models continuously followed throughout the project. Annex 4 shows the RESTORE_Lib **Available Units**, currently with 86 units contained in the library.

3.1.2. Workflow of RESTORE Model Development and Availability of Process Simulations

With the RESTORE Virtual Tool being available online for stakeholders, the use cases can be used as templates to simulate modified cases interactively by anyone interested in the technology. Additionally, stakeholders will be able to create their own testing cases, such that the number of different application examples will grow continuously. For displaying simulation results and dissemination of selected use cases, projects can be embedded in websites. The workflow how RESTORE Models are developed and made available for different stakeholders is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Workflow of model development and process simulation.

3.2. The Use-Cases simulated in RESTORE Virtual Tool

The RESTORE Virtual Tool will host and showcase the RESTORE virtual Use-Cases. The overall RESTORE concept will be virtually implemented and optimized for six DHC Use-Cases with real data from the Use-Case providers.

The six Virtual Use-Cases will analyze potential configurations for integrating the RESTORE technology and RES, potentially available on site, into different plants connected with DHC networks. They integrate with real DHC networks spread over different locations in Europe, including large and small district heating networks, as illustrated in Figure 6.

Figure 6: RESTORE Use-Cases.

- **Use-Case I** deals with a residential and industrial DH with biomass and solar collectors in Denmark.
- **Use-Case II** deals with the integration of different heat sources in DH of a cement factory in Austria.
- **Use-Case III** integrates RESTORE with different heat sources in DH of a paper mill in Slovakia.
- **Use-Case IV** deals with the integration of different heat sources in DH of a steel industry in Italy.
- **Use-Case V** concerns the district heating with geothermal technology in a plant in Germany.
- **Use-Case VI** deals with the small-scale DHC network of POLIMI University Campus in Italy. See Annexes VI to XI for a more detailed description of the RESTORE Use-cases.

3.2.1. Specification of the high-level modelling data to implementing the Use-Cases

The specification of the high-level modelling data and requirements for implementing the RESTORE Use-Cases was defined in D1.4 [3], considering the boundary conditions imposed by each specific use-case application. In this context, D1.4 provides a general basis to be considered as a guide during the project process modelling and Use-Cases implementation.

In general terms, the use cases' models calculation will require the following inputs to be implemented using IPSE GO: User Input: (a) For the Charging Mode coming from Waste Heat: Maximum of Q_{Waste} / Maximum of E_{Waste} ; Number of Hours; Number of Months; Temperature of Waste Heat. User Input: (b) For the Discharging Mode going to District Heating (DH): Supply Temperature to DH; Return Temperature from DH, Max. And Min. of Q_{DH} in operation. Internal Input and main outputs can be observed in Figure 7, about the Use-Cases Models' Basic Information [3].

Figure 7: Use-Cases Models' Basic Information (from RESTORE WP1-T1.4-D1.4).

4. RESTORE Use-Case I

USE-CASE I: Residential / Industrial DHC with Biomass and Solar Collectors and industrial WEH - Location: BRONDERSLEV PLANT (CSP INTEGRATED WITH BIOMASS-ORC) – Denmark.

- **Use-Case provider:** Aalborg CSP, based on detailed engineering data and integration experience.
- **Use-Case Area of Application:** District heating for the city of Brønderslev, Biomass and Solar collectors as renewable technologies to provide heat to the District.
- **Expected goals to be achieved:** Maximization of renewable energy integration in the district, and optimum waste heat utilization from local industry for highly efficient seasonal storage of electricity.

Figure 8: RESTORE proposed solution in Use-Case I.

4.1. Use-Case I Description

Brønderslev Forsyning A/S has implemented a District Heating concept: power and district heating supply are generated in its own combined heat and power unit which is one of the most efficient plants worldwide due to the combination of solar, biomass and HPs. After a comprehensive feasibility study and 0.8MWth test facility campaign Brønderslev Forsyning A/S started the construction of a CSP plant to supply 16.6 MWth which has been in operation since March 2018. The solar energy plant is based on the parabolic trough technology consisting of 40 rows of 125m U-shaped mirrors with an aperture area of 27,000 m² and glass vacuum tube receiver. Thermal oil is used as heat transfer fluid with a maximum temperature of 330°C. The system was designed and constructed by project partner AAL. Collected energy can be stored in a thermal energy storage unit based on pressurized water tanks that are connected to an existing biomass-fired ORC power plant or directly provide heat to the local district heating system adapting its operation temperature according to the specific needs of the district's energy system. Similarly, the biomass boiler provides heat to the ORC or the district. The ORC (40 CHPRS SPLIT) is manufactured by project partner TURBODEN and has a power output of about 3.8 MWe and was originally fed by thermal oil coming both from the 2 biomass boilers. Overall system represents an advanced DH solution based on non-conventional hybrid solar-

biomass ORC plant able to provide sustainable heat and electricity. District heating return and supply water temperature are 50°C and 72°C.

4.2. Use-Case I - RESTORE proposed solution

The virtual pilot will be based on the energy system described above, integrating a specifically optimized RESTORE energy storage unit. The existing parabolic trough solar collector field can then charge the TCES system during summer months, thereby solar heat is stored for heating in winter. Additionally, residual heat from industry or excess low-temperature heat from solar collectors in the district is used to efficiently store off-peak cheap electricity.

4.3. High-level modelling data for Use-Case I

Based on the information identified in Figure 7, concerning the specification of the high-level modelling data and requirements for implementing the RESTORE Use-Cases (defined in D1.4 [3]), WP5-Task T5.4 needs to adapt the required input data and the expected outputs for each of the six Use-Cases in RESTORE project. Hence, for the current Use-Case I, specific information from the template (shown in Figure 9) is requested from the Use-Case Provider.

Figure 9: Use-Case I Models' Basic Information Requirement.

Further details about the modelling and the results of virtually implementing this use-case will be published, as a result of sub-task T5.4.1, in Deliverable D5.4 (Implementation and validation of RESTORE Use-Case I: Residential / Industrial DH with Biomass and Solar Collectors), and made openly available in the [RESTORE project's Zenodo Community account](#).

5. RESTORE Use-Case II

USE-CASE II: Integration of different Cement Industry heat sources in DHC - Location: GMUNDEN CEMENT FACTORY - Gmunden, Austria.

- **Use-Case provider:** CENER & TU-WIEN based on detailed engineering data and integration experience from the owner Rohrdorfer of the Gmunden cement plant.
- **Use-Case Area of Application:** Analysis of potential configurations of integrating the RESTORE technology into the Cement production plant and its relation to the neighbouring heat consumers.
- **Expected goals to be achieved:** Maximization of renewable energy integration and optimum WEH utilization from the factory for highly efficient seasonal storage of electricity using RESTORE.

5.1. Use-Case II Description

The Gmunden site cement plant of Rohrdorfer group has currently the capacity of ~1.900 ton/day of cement clinker, with a district heating connection (capacity of ~8 MWth). The clinker process offers multiple options of heat integration with district heating and cooling, either via the WEH coming from air cooled clinker coolers, or from the off gas from cyclone tower. In the case of a waste heat steam cycle plant such as in the Rohrdorf site, also, or from extraction steam from a steam turbine can be used which itself is fed by steam from the waste heat recovery steam generator. The installation of a waste heat steam generator is under consideration in the frame of a national research project. The state-of-the-art cement factory in Gmunden produces huge amounts of WEH that cannot be used by the cement production process itself. Its recent connection to a local district heating network allowed 8 MW thermal power to be provided covering the heat demand for roughly 1,000 homes. Additional excess heat is available, especially during summer months when no space heating is required.

Figure 10: RESTORE proposed solution in Use-Case II.

5.2. Use-Case II - RESTORE proposed solution

Within the RESTORE project, the virtual pilot will simulate the integration of the developed concept within the industrial plant in order to maximize WEH utilization and RES integration for seasonal storage of heat using cheap off-peak electricity. RESTORE concept allows to

transfer excess heat from the summer to the winter, when cement plants are typically shutting down for at least 6 weeks thus continuously providing DH with carbon free heat. In this virtual pilot, the integration of additional RES will be studied. The RESTORE project counts with the support of the owner of the plant (member of the RESTORE project External Stakeholders and Advisory Board ESAB), being actively involved in configuring the virtual pilot and in supplying the needed technical data as well as important considerations for the system as final user of the RESTORE system.

5.3. High-level modelling data for Use-Case II

Based on the information identified in Figure 7, concerning the specification of the high-level modelling data and requirements for implementing the RESTORE Use-Cases (defined in D1.4 [3]), WP5-Task T5.4 needs to adapt the required input data and the expected outputs for each of the six Use-Cases in RESTORE project. Hence, for the current Use-Case II, specific information from the template (shown in Figure 11) is requested from the Use-Case Provider.

Figure 11: Use-Case II Models' Basic Information Requirement.

Further details about the modelling and the results of virtually implementing this use-case will be published, as a result of sub-task T5.4.2, in Deliverable D5.5 (Implementation and validation of RESTORE Use-Case II: Integration of different heat sources in DH of Cement Industry), and made openly available in the [RESTORE project's Zenodo Community account](#).

6. RESTORE Use-Case III

USE-CASE III: Integration of different heat sources in DHC of Paper Mills Industry -
 Location: MONDI SCP PLANT - Ružomberok, Slovakia

- **Use-Case provider:** ANDRITZ (AND), based on detailed engineering data and integration experience from its customer MONDI SCP in Slovakia.
- **Use-Case Area of Application:** Analysis of potential configurations for integrating the RESTORE technology into plants of the Pulp and Paper Industry connected to DH and RES.
- **Expected goals to be achieved:** Maximize the renewable energy integration and optimize WEH utilization from the factory for highly efficient seasonal heat storage.

Figure 12: RESTORE proposed solution in Use-Case III.

6.1. Use-Case III Description

Mondi SCP in Ružomberok is one of Mondi's largest plants and is the biggest integrated mill producing paper and pulp in the Slovak Republic, with a production capacity of 560,000 tonnes of uncoated fine paper, 66,000 tonnes of packaging paper and 100,000 tonnes of market pulp. After its latest investment into a new recovery boiler, the mill is 100% energy self-sufficient with over 94% of its energy coming from renewable resources. The wood comes from certified, well-managed forests. The production continuously decreases footprint on the environment. Part of the heat produced by the Mondi mill is used for the district heating system in the form of 5 bar steam. Steam enters a heat exchanger station, where heat exchangers transfer heat into water. Hot water is pumped via a distribution network into the city, local heat exchangers and flowing back to the steam/ water heat exchanger station to gain heat again.

6.2. Use-Case III - RESTORE proposed solution

The utilization of the following energy sources will be explored and integrated in RESTORE concept and use to store heat on seasonal base: (i) utilisation of waste steam in case of reduced heat demand in district heating (e.g.: summer time), (ii) flue gas recovery from boilers

at LT which is not used so far, (iii) hot water streams available at site which may be used for water preheating or HP energy input. Moreover, synergies with thermal and electrical based energy sources will be investigated considering also adding new RES sources in order to limit additional fossil fuel consumption. The expected outcome is a huge reduction of the GHG through a high increment in the RES share and the waste heat capacity factor.

6.3. High-level modelling data for Use-Case III

Based on the information identified in Figure 7, concerning the specification of the high-level modelling data and requirements for implementing the RESTORE Use-Cases (defined in D1.4 [3]), WP5-Task T5.4 needs to adapt the required input data and the expected outputs for each of the six Use-Cases in RESTORE project. Hence, for the current Use-Case III, specific information from the template (shown in Figure 13) is requested from the Use-Case Provider.

Figure 13: Use-Case III Models' Basic Information Requirement.

Further details about the modelling and the results of virtually implementing this use-case will be published, as a result of sub-task T5.4.3, in Deliverable D5.6 (Implementation and validation of RESTORE Use-Case III: Integration of different heat sources in DH of Paper Mills Industry), and made openly available in the [RESTORE project's Zenodo Community account](#).

7. RESTORE Use-Case IV

USE-CASE IV: Integration of different heat sources in DHC of Steel-working industry -
 Location: BRESCIA – Italy.

- **Use-Case provider:** TURBODEN based on detailed engineering data and integration experience from the potential final user and Use-Case provider Alfa Acciai, from Brescia.
- **Use-Case Area of Application:** The use case will apply the RESTORE concept to a DHC network linked to one of the largest Electric Arc Furnace steel mills in Italy.
- **Expected goals to be achieved:** Achieve higher efficiency of Alfa Acciai production process, improve HP utilization during summer season and increase share on local DH.

Figure 14: RESTORE proposed solution in Use-Case IV.

7.1. Use-Case IV Description

Alfa Acciai is one of the largest Electric Arc Furnace Steel Mill in Italy. It started producing steel in Brescia in the mid-1950s. The Alfa Acciai Group has been increasingly oriented towards customer service, by focusing on the production of steel for the reinforcement of concrete, while respecting the environment and the worker health and safety in the workplace. Alfa Acciai site in Brescia is composed by 2 Electric Arc Furnace units and 3 rolling mills. Current strategy for waste heat recovery system based on a large HP able to recover WEH from the cooling system of the “pipe to pipe” circuit of the furnaces. The temperature of available heat is in the range of 30°-40°C and can be upgraded up to 90°C through the HP and used for district heating instead of being wasted. The recovered upgraded thermal energy will be used and integrated in the local district heating of municipality of Brescia and distributed to the final users in order to satisfy the heat demand in a smart and green way.

7.2. Use-Case IV - RESTORE proposed solution

RESTORE technology can dramatically increase the utilization of existing equipment and WEH utilization during summer months when heat is not required by DH and so the HPs are not working. With RESTORE heat released by EAF is upgraded to High Temperature all year long: during winter heat is directly used by DH while during summer heat is exploited by RESTORE HP and allows storing energy for the winter season. Integrated solution with renewable energies and synergies with other industry subsystems will be investigated. The expected impact is a strong increase of HP capacity factor and a final energy provided to the DH network nearly double of the current state of the art.

7.3. High-level modelling data for Use-Case IV

Based on the information identified in Figure 7, concerning the specification of the high-level modelling data and requirements for implementing the RESTORE Use-Cases (defined in D1.4 [3]), WP5-Task T5.4 needs to adapt the required input data and the expected outputs for each of the six Use-Cases in RESTORE project. Hence, for the current Use-Case IV, specific information from the template (shown in Figure 15) is requested from the Use-Case Provider.

Figure 15: Use-Case IV Models' Basic Information Requirement.

Further details about the modelling and the results of virtually implementing this use-case will be published, as a result of sub-task T5.4.4, in Deliverable D5.7 (Implementation and validation of RESTORE Use-Case IV: Integration of different heat sources in DH of Steel working industry), and made openly available in the [RESTORE project's Zenodo Community account](#).

8. RESTORE Use-Case V

USE-CASE V: District heating with Geothermal Technology - Location: Geothermie Holzkirchen Plant, Holzkirchen- Germany.

- **Use-Case provider:** TURBODEN based on detailed engineering data and integration experience from its Use-Case provider Geothermie Holzkirchen GmbH from Holzkirchen in Germany.
- **Use-Case Area of Application:** The use case will apply the RESTORE concept to a DHC network (local utility of Holzkirchen) with Geothermal Technology.
- **Expected goals to be achieved:** Maximization of the geothermal heat exploitation and optimum WEH utilization for highly efficient seasonal storage of heat.

8.1. Use-Case V Description

Geothermie Holzkirchen GmbH is a wholly owned subsidiary of the local utility of Holzkirchen, a town located in the south of Munich, Germany. The existing conditions for developing geothermal energy are particularly favourable in the southern German Molasse basin, as there is particularly hot water at the appropriate depth (500 meters). Heat can be used as direct supply to district heating and, from a temperature of around 120 degrees Celsius, electricity production is possible. It is estimated that in the long term up to 80 percent of Holzkirchen's district heating network demand can be covered with geothermal energy equivalent to around 10,000 tons of climate-damaging carbon dioxide avoided every year. An ORC from TUR is already installed on site to exploit geothermal hot water during the summer from a temperature of 140°C, producing a power output of 2.8 MWeI and contributing to the amortization of the project due to the feed-in tariff. Moreover, in order to increase the geothermal heat exploitation TUR will study a large HP in order to achieve higher flexibility in terms of heat and power production as well as increased geothermal utilisation.

Figure 16: RESTORE proposed solution in Use-Case V.

8.2. Use-Case V - RESTORE proposed solution

RESTORE technology can be integrated with geothermal energy exploiting it during summer to store heat for the cold season. From this point of view RESTORE is a competitive solution against ORC and this Use-Case provides a unique possibility to evaluate and compare the economic feasibility of both solutions. The integration of additional RES technologies due to RESTORE technology will be investigated. Expected impact are a dramatic increase of energy to the DH and a marked reduction of GHG emission. Availability of HP during summer and other RES will be investigated.

8.3. High-level modelling data for Use-Case V

Based on the information identified in Figure 7, concerning the specification of the high-level modelling data and requirements for implementing the RESTORE Use-Cases (defined in D1.4 [3]), WP5-Task T5.4 needs to adapt the required input data and the expected outputs for each of the six Use-Cases in RESTORE project. Hence, for the current Use-Case V, specific information from the template (shown in Figure 17) is requested from the Use-Case Provider.

Figure 17: Use-Case V Models' Basic Information Requirement.

Further details about the modelling and the results of virtually implementing this use-case will be published, as a result of sub-task T5.4.5, in Deliverable D5.8 (Implementation and validation of RESTORE Use-Case V: District heating with Geothermal Technology), and made openly available in the [RESTORE project's Zenodo Community account](#).

9. RESTORE Use-Case VI

USE-CASE VI: Small scale DHC network of Politecnico di Milano campus - Location: POLIMI CAMPUS, Milan - Italy.

- **Use-Case provider:** POLIMI, based on detailed engineering data and integration experience from its small DHC network.
- **Use-Case Area of Application:** This use case aims to exploit RESTORE in small-scale DHC networks.
- **Expected goals to be achieved:** Apply the RESTORE concept to a small DHC network available at Politecnico di Milano campus and representative of small size decentralized solutions.

9.1. Use-Case VI Description

Politecnico di Milano adopts a small DH network to provide electricity and heat to a relevant fraction of campus offices, classrooms and laboratories serving approximately 120.000 mq. Moreover, cooling is also provided to some buildings during the summer season. Maximum thermal power request is around 15 MWth and thermal plant of the DHC encompasses three natural gas boilers of 6 MWth each and one natural gas internal combustion engine in CHP configuration able to provide 2 MWeI plus 1.8 MWth. Cooling power 1.25 MW is generated by one absorption chiller (LiBr) exploiting CHP unit waste heat. The CHP unit is operated in thermal load following and most of electrical energy (80%) is for internal consumption while the remaining (20%) is sold to the grid. Annual hours of operations of the CHP unit thanks to the integration with the cooling network is around 5000 h. In addition to the DHC network, the Energy Department of Politecnico di Milano located in Bovisa Campus can also provide accurate information on the availability of solar PV energy thanks to the availability of PV panels of different technologies for a total 75 kWel and a storage system constituted by 70kWh Lithium-ion Samsung battery. All the quantities related to DHC network, the thermal plant operation and the PV fields are continuously monitored and detailed dataset are available for the last years of operation.

Figure 18: RESTORE proposed solution in Use-Case VI.

9.2. Use-Case VI - RESTORE proposed solution

The POLIMI Campus Use-Case aims to understand the role of RESTORE technology in small decentralized DHC networks and to understand the constraints in terms of space in urban contexts. First, an evaluation of fuel shifting from natural gas to biogas will be investigated, then the RESTORE concept is implemented understanding the synergies with district cooling operation and RES integration. Final results would assess the environmental and economic sustainability of seasonal thermal storage.

9.3. High-level modelling data for Use-Case VI

Based on the information identified in Figure 7, concerning the specification of the high-level modelling data and requirements for implementing the RESTORE Use-Cases (defined in D1.4 [3]), WP5-Task T5.4 needs to adapt the required input data and the expected outputs for each of the six Use-Cases in RESTORE project. Hence, for the current Use-Case VI, specific information from the template (shown in Figure 19) is requested from the Use-Case Provider.

Figure 19: Use-Case VI Models' Basic Information Requirement.

Further details about the modelling and the results of virtually implementing this use-case will be published, as a result of sub-task T5.4.6, in Deliverable D5.9 (Implementation and validation of RESTORE Use-Case VI: Small-scale DHC network of Politecnico di Milano campus), and made openly available in the [RESTORE project's Zenodo Community account](#).

10. Remarks & Further Work

This report was designed to guide the WP5-T5.4 involved partners in the development of their use-cases implementation tasks, up to RESTORE project month M46, serving also as input for the production of the deliverables D5.4, D5.5, D5.6, D5.7, D5.8, and D5.9.

The work of task T5.4 directly contributes to the practice of the Replication Strategy steps in task T5.5, which aims that selected stakeholders create their own testing cases within and beyond the project lifetime.

The RESTORE Virtual Tool (under <https://ipsego.app/>) will be available for both project partners and end-users (during the project lifetime and beyond) to assist all project phases (design, development, testing, replication cases, and exploitation), demonstrating the project's Use-Cases and interacting with the RESTORE stakeholder ecosystem for exploitation purposes. It will host the simulated use cases and will remain online after the project ends, to stimulate a new technological direction and the emergence of a European innovation ecosystem around the RESTORE paradigm.

As part of the outcomes of WP5 Task T5.5 [8], SIMTECH will also provide online, on a dedicated website for the use-cases results, compact description of the six RESTORE Use-Cases developed in the project, including their embedded models from the IPSE GO platform. This information will be accessible via the link: <https://usecases.restore-dhc.eu/use-cases/>.

11. References

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Annex I. RESTORE Virtual Tool powered by IPSE GO

Landing Page of the RESTORE Virtual Tool powered by IPSE GO, showing the navigation Tabs for: Project Overview; RESTORE_Lib Available Units; and RESTORE Example Projects.

The screenshot displays the RESTORE Virtual Tool interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the IPSE GO logo and user information. A sidebar on the left contains navigation options: Dashboard, Projects, Groups, Libraries (selected), Licenses, Profile, and Preferences. The main content area shows the 'Libraries > RESTORE_Lib' page. A banner image depicts a sustainable energy landscape with wind turbines, solar panels, and buildings. Below the banner, the title 'Horizon 2020 RESTORE Project Model Library' is centered. A search bar is positioned above a grid of 24 available units, organized into three columns. Each unit is represented by an icon, a name, and a brief description.

General	86 Available Units	Example Projects
gear (3 models) gears	generator (2 models) generator	G_OR_Htex (3 models) heat exchanger for transfer from gas on hot side to organic fluid on cold side
G_Pipe (2 models) pipe for gas streams	G_Sink sink for a gas stream	G_Source source for a gas stream
mech_loss mechanical loss	motor (2 models) motor	optimization optimization element
OR_Boiler (2 models) simple boiler model for ORC fluids	OR_Compressor (2 models) compressor for ORC fluids	OR_Condenser (2 models) condenser for ORC fluids, water cooled
OR_Condenser_a (2 models) condenser for ORC fluids, air cooled, dry	OR_Connector connector for ORC streams to be used in closed loops	OR_Expander (2 models) expander for ORC fluids
OR_G_Htex (3 models) heat exchanger for transfer from ORC fluid on hot side to gas on cold side	OR_Htex (3 models) general purpose heat exchanger for ORC fluids	OR_Heat_sink (2 models) heat sink for usage with OR streams
OR_Heat_source (2 models) heat source for usage with OR streams	OR_Mixer (2 models) mixer for ORC streams	OR_Pipe (3 models) pipe for ORC fluids
OR_Pump pump for ORC fluids	OR_Properties (2 models) calculation and display of physical properties of OR fluids	OR_Separator (3 models) vapour-liquid separator for ORC fluids
OR_Splitter (2 models) splitter for ORC streams	OR_Sink sink for an ORC stream	OR_Source source for an ORC stream

Annex II. RESTORE Virtual Tool – Projects Page

RESTORE Virtual Tool powered by IPSE GO, showing the available RESTORE process models.

The screenshot displays the IPSE GO RESTORE Virtual Tool interface. The top navigation bar includes the IPSE GO logo, a search bar, and links for Help, Support, About, and the user profile (RESTORE User). The left sidebar contains navigation options: Dashboard, Projects (selected), Groups, Libraries, Licenses, Profile, and Preferences. The main content area is titled 'Example Projects' and features a search bar and a grid of project models. Each model card includes a thumbnail image of the process flow diagram, a title, and a brief description.

Project Name	Description
Demo_HP	Basic compression heat pump process using R134a as working fluid. Low and high temperature
Demo_ORC_basic	Basic Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) Process using n-Pentane as working fluid. Condenser is
Demo_ORC_with_Recu...	Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) process using toluene as working fluid with an internal
Demo_RESTORE_rORC	Demonstration model of the reversible ORC process for charging and discharging
RESTORE rORC HP mo...	Demonstration model of the reversible ORC process for charging the thermochemical
RESTORE rORC ORC ...	Demonstration model of the reversible ORC process for discharging the thermochemical
RESTORE rORC with T...	Reference design model which can serve as a starting point for adaption to individual use-cases.
TCM_Charging_Step	Model depicting the charging step of the thermochemical material. Different storage
TCM_Discharging_Step	Model depicting the discharging step of the thermochemical material. Different storage

Annex III. RESTORE TCES Charging Model

RESTORE TCES Charging Model within IPSE GO.

The screenshot displays the IPSE GO software interface for a TCES charging model. The main window shows a detailed process flow diagram with various components and their associated data. The diagram includes pumps, mixers, and heat exchangers, with data labels for mass flow, enthalpy, pressure, and temperature. A status bar at the bottom indicates "No issues detected".

Object Manager Table:

Class	Object
OR_Sink	OR_Sink001
OR_Source	OR_Source001
OR_wall_htex	OR_wall_htex001
OR_Xprescription	OR_Xprescription001
T_Connector	T_Connector002
T_Heat_sink	T_Heat_sink001
T_Pump	T_Pump001
T_TCM_Htex	T_TCM_Htex002
TCM_Mixer	TCM_Mixer001
TCM_Pump	TCM_Pump001
TCM_Pump	TCM_Pump001a
TCM_Reactor_Char...	TCM_Reactor_Char...
TCM_Separator	TCM_Separator001
TCM_Sink	TCM_Sink001
TCM_Source	TCM_Source001
TCM_T_Htex	TCM_T_Htex001
W_Heat_sink	W_Heat_sink001
W_Sink	W_Sink001
OR_Stream	OR_Stream001
OR_Stream	OR_Stream002
OR_Stream	OR_Stream003

Annex IV. RESTORE TCES Discharging Model

RESTORE TCES Discharging Model within IPSE GO.

The screenshot displays the IPSE GO software interface for a TCES Discharging Model. The main workspace shows a detailed process flow diagram with various components and their associated data. The data labels include mass flow rates (kg/s), energy flows (kJ/kg), pressures (bar), and temperatures (°C).

Object Manager Table:

Class	Object
OR_Sink	OR_Sink001
OR_Source	OR_Source001
T_Connector	T_Connector004
T_Heat_sink	T_Heat_sink003
T_Mixer	T_Mixer001
T_Pump	T_Pump003
T_Splitter	T_Splitter001
T_TCM_Htex	T_TCM_Htex001
T_W_Htex	T_W_Htex002
TCM_Heat_sink	TCM_Heat_sink002
TCM_Mixer	TCM_Mixer006
TCM_Pump	TCM_Pump011
TCM_Pump	TCM_Pump012
TCM_Reactor_Disch...	TCM_Reactor_Disch...
TCM_Separator	TCM_Separator006
TCM_Sink	TCM_Sink004
TCM_Source	TCM_Source001
TCM_T_Htex	TCM_T_Htex002
W_Pump	W_Pump002
W_Source	W_Source003
wall_OR_htex	wall_OR_htex001

Object Manager: Object Mana... Dataset Mana... Chart Mana...

Status: ✓ No issues detected IPSE GO v1.11.3 - RESTORE_Lib

Annex V. RESTORE Reference Design Model

RESTORE Reference Design Model which can be used as a starting point for setting up a use-case.

The screenshot displays the IPSE GO software interface for modeling a RESTORE rORC with TCES system. The main workspace shows a detailed schematic diagram of the system, including components like generators, motors, compressors, condensers, expanders, pumps, and valves. The diagram is annotated with various parameters and labels, such as 'rORC with TCES Charging and Discharging', 'TCES HT mode - charging', and 'TCES ORC mode - discharging'. Below the schematic, there are several data tables providing detailed parameters for different components, including pumps, turbines, and heat exchangers. The interface also features a sidebar with a search function and a list of objects, and a top navigation bar with options like Project, View, Objects, and Calculation.

Annex VI. RESTORE_Lib Components

RESTORE_Lib Component Models (as of July 2025). The model library was produced using IPSEpro-MDK and is used in both IPSEpro and IPSE GO.

G_OR_HtEx (3 models) heat exchanger for transfer from gas on hot side to organic fluid on cold side		
G_Source source for a gas stream		
optimization optimization element		
OR_Condenser (2 models) condenser for ORC fluids, water cooled		
OR_Expander (2 models) expander for ORC fluids		
OR_Heat_sink (2 models) heat sink for usage with OR streams		
OR_Pipe (3 models) pipe for ORC fluids		
OR_Separator (3 models) vapour-liquid separator for ORC fluids		
OR_Source source for an ORC stream		
OR_Valve valve for ORC fluid		
OR_wall_HtEx heat exchanger with wall transferring heat from organic fluid (OR) to another side		
TCM_Connector (2 models) connector for TCM to be used in closed loops		
TCM_HtEx heat exchanger for transfer from TCM fluid on hot side to TCM fluid on cold side		
TCM_Pump pump for TCM fluids		
TCM_Separator separator for TCM stream		
TCM_Splitter splitter for TCM streams		
TCM_W_Separator separator for water from TCM stream		
T_Heat_source heat source for heat transfer fluids		
T_OR_HtEx (3 models) heat exchanger for transfer from thermofluid on hot side to ORC fluids on cold side		
T_Splitter (2 models) splitter for heat transfer fluid streams		
T_TCM_HtEx heat exchanger for transfer from thermofluid on hot side to TCM fluid on cold side		
W_Compressor compressor for steam		
W_Heat_source heat source for water streams		
W_Pipe (3 models) pipe for water		
W_Source source for a water stream		
W_Valve valve for water		
flow_meter (3 models) flow meter		
time_counter (2 models) time counter used for measuring and displaying time intervals		
wall_T_htex heat exchanger with wall transferring heat from wall to thermofluid (T)		